

RM ROADMAP

D4.6 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

The RM ROADMAP Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (DCE) Report summarises the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Activities of the RM ROADMAP Consortium for the duration of the project. In particular, the report presents the impact of dissemination and communication activities conducted by the Consortium in promoting the RM ROADMAP project's results and outcomes.

WP4: Community, Communication and Dissemination. Crowdhelix

June 2025

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

Project full title

“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area”

Project acronym

RM Roadmap

Grant Agreement no.

101058475

D4.6: Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Report

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RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

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List of Abbreviations, Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
ASTP	Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals
CHX	Crowdhelix
D	Deliverable
DCE	Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation
EARMA	European Association of Research Managers and Administrators
KCP	Knowledge and Community Platform
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NGOs	Non-governmental Organisations
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RM	Research Management
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (DCE) Report (D4.6) provides a comprehensive overview of the RM ROADMAP project's dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities throughout its duration. This report serves as the final progress report for Work Package (WP)4, which focuses on Community, Communication, and Dissemination. It is the sixth deliverable of WP4 and details the activities and impacts resulting from actions taken by the RM ROADMAP consortium partners. The main objectives of the WP have been to communicate and inform relevant stakeholders about the project's activities and ensure effective dissemination of project results among the Research Management community.

The report outlines the community activities, communication channels, and interactions, comparing them to the goals established in the first deliverable of WP4, D4.1 Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan, which was delivered in month M6 (February 2023). It builds upon the activities and impact detailed in [D4.4. "The Preliminary Report on Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation \(DCE\)"](#), which was delivered in month M12 (August 2023).

The report demonstrates that the RM ROADMAP project has successfully met its objectives related to communication, dissemination, and impact. Furthermore, it has exceeded the success criteria and key performance indicators (KPIs) defined in the Grant Agreement (GA). The RM ROADMAP project is funded by the European Commission under GA No. 101058475.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

RM-ROADMAP supports research management (RM) capacity in Europe. Over 36 months, the project has charted a course for EU research management's (RM) future and created an inclusive community to support its delivery. The overarching goal of the RM Roadmap has been to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

Such a broad outreach has been made feasible by leveraging the research management community's volunteering power in combination with a common IT environment, engaging with networks (of networks), and establishing a new Ambassador Network. The IT environment is the Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP). Currently, most networking and best practice exchange in Europe occurs through volunteering. In most cases, this happens with the support of the employers of those research managers.

The RM Roadmap's KCP comprises two systems: one for co-creation (**the EARMA co-creation platform**) and another for dissemination and impact acceleration (**CrowdHelix RM Helix**).

- The Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP) is embedded within the EARMA website (and can be accessed through the [link](#).)
- RM Helix is a virtual collaboration community established and curated on the CrowdHelix open innovation platform.

This co-creation process has united existing communities and expanded them to achieve two main objectives:

- To create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap;
- To inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities.

Eight partners have worked together on the RM ROADMAP project: the European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (Belgium), HETFA Research Institute (Hungary), Nova University Lisbon (Portugal), Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (the Netherlands), CrowdHelix Limited (Ireland), The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus), and associated partners Janssen Pharmaceuticals (J&J) and Una Europa (Belgium).

The success of this project depended on the involvement of the research management community across Europe and beyond. Research support professionals of all levels were invited to participate in RM ROADMAP and were encouraged to join, share their views and work together to shape the future of the research management profession in Europe.

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1.2. Deliverable Purpose

As an output of the WP4: Community, Communication and Dissemination, D4.6 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report” is directly linked with D4.1 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan” and D4.4. “Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report”. The document reports on the communication and dissemination activities that have been undertaken throughout the project lifecycle and demonstrates the achievements of the RM ROADMAP Consortium.

Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation are integral parts of RM ROADMAP’s development processes. While communication, dissemination and exploitation activities have been managed and administered in WP4 (Community, Communication, Dissemination), related activities have arisen across all other WPs of the project. Therefore, the management of DCE activities involved close collaboration and communication among the partner organisations.

Throughout the project's lifetime, the RM ROADMAP Consortium has realised the following communication and dissemination tasks, which will be further elaborated on in the report.

- T4.1: Communication Activities
- T4.2: Dissemination Activities
- T4.3: Collaborative Virtual Ecosystem: Research Managers Helix development and management
- T4.4: Outreach Activities
- T4.5: Clustering with sister and other EU projects
- T4.6: Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP)

The deliverable is public and, therefore, mainly addressed to the RM ROADMAP Consortium partners, the European Commission (funding authority), and other audiences interested in learning more about and engaging with the project.

2. Milestones, Monitoring and Performance

The table below lists the performance measures, linked objectives and targets for Dissemination Communication and Exploitation as presented in Deliverable D4.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan and the RM ROADMAP Grant Agreement. The RM ROADMAP project has surpassed the key performance indicators (KPIs) established during the proposal stage, as illustrated in the table below. In several areas, such as RM Helix membership, website visit counts, social media followers, and impressions, the project has either doubled or quadrupled the initial targets. This success has significantly enhanced the overall impact of the project.

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Table 1 - RM ROADMAP Milestones & KPIs

ACTIVITIES	Milestone / Schedule	Key Performance Indicator(s)	Target	Status
Research Management Helix	Scoping from M1; established in line with KCP; maintained at least 5 years beyond the project or as long as valuable	Number of organisations represented in followers	150	3636 organisations, 1064 users, 78 countries (as of 20 June 2025)
Project website	M1 onwards and 5 years beyond the term [Project Milestone 1]	Number of visits	2000	90,960
Social media	Established at project KO	Number of followers	300 followers across Twitter, LinkedIn, ResearchGate	2 channels LinkedIn: 2364 followers X/Twitter: 415 followers
		Impressions (general public reach)	20 000	>120000 impressions
Partners' websites	As defined by partners task involvement	Number of pages	1 dedicated webpage area per partner website	2 dedicated webpage area per partner website
Newsletters	One per year starting M12	Open rate per newsletter to mailing list	25% open rate per newsletter	First Newsletter Open Rate: 46.9% Second Newsletter Open Rate: 68% Third Newsletter Open Rate:
		Number of views on social media.	(No target)	
Media	Continuous before,	Number of press releases/popular	6	15

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Engagements	during and after project	articles		
		Number of media appearances per partner	6	
Project workshops	Annual	Number of overall participants	>80 per workshop	>230
		Events attended by policy representatives	4	4
Project final conference	M34	Number of participants	>200	
Other international events	As per target event schedule (Appendix B)	Number of participations / appearances	10	68
Other regional events		Number of participations / appearances per partner	6	
Publications	As results are available, continues beyond the project term	Number of articles	3-4	

3. Project Audience

Over the course of the project, the RM ROADMAP Consortium identified and refined its list of stakeholders who have an interest or influence in the project or would be affected in some way by its progress and expected results. The consortium engaged with these stakeholder/audience categories through different communication and content types with specific objectives and targeted messaging. This enabled the project team to optimise resources by ensuring that messaging remains relevant.

These groups are listed below:

- Academic Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) – RM professionals
- Academic RTOs – Academics
- Research Manager Professional Community
- Public Agencies
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and nonprofit organisations
- Policy makers
- Commercial RTOs
- Commercial Industry
- Civil Society
- Citizen organisations
- Projects

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- Associations
- Policy Makers, including ministries

The EARMA Knowledge and Community Platform and the Research Management Helix, a virtual cluster community on the Crowdhelix open innovation platform, have been focal points for stakeholder engagement. More information on the Research Management Helix can be found in Section 6.1, while the activities related to the co-creation platform are detailed in the D4.5 Activity Report on Knowledge and Community Platform.

4. Engagement Strategy

As was stated in Deliverable 4.1. “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan”, the evolution of the DCE has unfolded over three phases. These included Initiation, Implementation and Sustaining and each phase was mapped against communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. The project leveraged traditional and digital marketing tools to engage the target stakeholders/audiences. Sustained exploitation of the project’s KERs is further explained and elaborated in D6.2 Final Sustainability Report.

In accordance with this, the RM ROADMAP project follows Horizon Europe guidelines to strategically, coherently, and effectively deliver targeted information to various audiences. The DCE plan and activities were designed, delivered, and evaluated according to the definitions of Horizon Europe guidelines by paying close attention to the following aspects.

Communication: *taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange*

Dissemination: *the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications via any medium.*

Exploitation: *the use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities.*

The evolution of the DCE has followed different aspects during its initiation, implementation, and sustaining periods, each focusing on different objectives.

Funded term →		Initiation	Implementation	Sustaining
Communication Dissemination Exploitation	Communication	Define identity, messaging and audiences, establish channels, make initial connections, build a following	Generate templates, designs and source content for various audiences, maintain following with regular updates	Transfer ownership of communications channels to suitable owner to maintain / wind down
	Dissemination	Agree protocols, collaboration strategies	Disseminate results to target audiences as they arise, following protocols; measure reach	Ensure continued, open access dissemination of results
	Exploitation	Identify potential KERs, initiate stakeholder mapping	Refine KERs, define pathways to impact and exploitation requirements analyse and execute stakeholder engagement plan	Directly engage with stakeholders to realise impact as per plan; market KERs on suitable channels as necessary (HRB, Innoradar, Helix)

Figure 1 - Evolution of DCE through the project

The underpinning RM ROADMAP Communication, dissemination, and exploitation objectives as presented in D4.1 are listed below:

Figure 2 - RM ROADMAP DCE Objectives in Relation to HE Guidelines

5. Tools, Content and Implementation

5.1. Roles and Protocols

The RM-Roadmap consortium agreed on site protocols and processes for managing communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. These elements are specified below:

As WP4 leaders, CHX have general responsibility for managing communications activities.

- Communication is talking to the outside world about the project, using information already in the public domain.
- Compliance is governed by Article 17 and Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement; partners must:
 - acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate); the EU flag must be at least as prominent as other logos.
 - include the disclaimer:
 - “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them.”
 - If communication is expected to have “major media impact”, the coordinator must be notified so they can inform the Project Officer in advance.
- Presentation slides, poster designs for printing and videos will be provided to be used by the partners without needing further permission.
- In order to coordinate, promote and support compliance in communication activities, partners

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should notify the C&D lead as soon as a communication activity is planned, by emailing rmroadmap@crowdhelix.com and/or updating the online tracker found on EMDesk.

- To multiply the benefit of individual activities, take photos and videos which can be used for other content (e.g. newsletter, social media).
- Following the activity, partners are required to update or complete the project tracker:
 - Add/confirm details including date, location, audience type and size.
 - Report social media campaigns (a significant post or series of posts clearly linked to the project on your own channel) as a single activity; ensure that you have access to the reach statistics.
- Partners are required to record specific costs related to these activities, as they will be requested with the financial report.

As WP4 leader, CHX has general responsibility for reporting on dissemination activities. Disseminating of own results in compliance with the following protocols is the responsibility of each partner.

- Dissemination is sharing the results of the project outside of the consortium in a publicly available format.
- Results are: *"Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights"*.
- From the Grant Agreement, Article 17 states the obligation to disseminate, further detailed on Annex 5 describing Open Science protocols.
- Dissemination is subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests; therefore, additional provisions are contained in the Consortium Agreement - these are to allow publication, not prevent it.
- Dissemination can be by any means: journal articles, conference presentations, white papers etc.
 - Partners are advised to limit disclosure of project results to formal publishing platforms. Social media, blog posts, interviews are difficult to monitor and control, and should therefore be used only for Communication as in the previous section. If you wish to disseminate in this way, contact the C&D lead.
 - For journal articles and conference submissions where the full article is submitted for peer review, send the final version of the article to rmroadmap@crowdhelix.com at least 30 days in advance of publication.
 - A formal notice is sent to all partners containing the submission, with a deadline for objections no less than 30 days later.
 - Objections must be specific and have corrective actions; i.e. either:
 - Remove confidential information.
 - Identify details that could prevent successful exploitation project results, needing a delay of up to 90 days to put protection in place.
 - With no valid objections, the publication can proceed.
 - For conferences where only an abstract is submitted:
 - If the abstract discloses project results, you must share it for review as per the above process prior to submission.
 - If the abstract only describes in general what will be presented, ensure a description of the content of your presentation is shared for review according to the above timelines prior to the actual presentation or event.
 - In all cases, discuss planned dissemination with the project partners at appropriate

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meetings well in advance.

- On Open Access for publications:
 - All peer-reviewed scientific publications relating must, at the latest at the time of publication, have the final peer-reviewed manuscript deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
 - Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to their articles to be able to comply.
 - Only publication fees (“APCs”) in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for claim under the project.
 - The [Directory of Open Journals](#) lists compliant venues for publishing.
- On Open Data:
 - Governed by the Data Management Plan (D5.2).
- Other:
 - Follow the Vancouver Rules for authorship.
 - Abide by the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment principles, in particular with respect to journal metrics.

As WP6 leaders, ASTP have general responsibility for exploitation planning and management.

- Exploitation is use of the results outside of the project, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing, and marketing a product or process, creating, and providing a service, standardisation or policy-making activities, and further research and innovation actions.
- As defined earlier for dissemination, results are: *"Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights"*.
- Provisions for Joint Ownership of results are found in the Consortium Agreement
- Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement states that:
 - funded beneficiaries must — up to four years after the end of the action — use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.
- If the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the results must be published to the Horizon Results Platform (HRP).
- Adding Results to the HRP is the responsibility of the coordinator, and may require following the Dissemination protocols in the previous section.
- The HRP accepts only Key Exploitable Results (KERs), defined as Results selected due to high potential to be exploited, based on degree of innovation, availability, and potential impact.

5.2. Dissemination and Communication Overview

The dissemination and communication channels for the RM ROADMAP project were developed and organised according to the RM ROADMAP DCE plan D4.1. The aim was to raise awareness about the project, engage the identified stakeholders, and promote the project's goals and outcomes. The project website and social media accounts provided a regular flow of information, facilitated open dialogue with stakeholder groups, and ensured promotion of the project both throughout Europe and internationally.

5.3. RM Roadmap Identity and Support Materials

The brand identity guided the design of the project logo, document template, and PowerPoint slide deck. The slide deck has been shared with all project partners and is accessible in the project's EMDESK space, allowing for use without the need for additional permission.

The project identity has been developed, including a logo and document templates. As part of D4.1, a set of branding guidelines has been developed to ensure a cohesive visual identity. These guidelines ensured that the logo was used consistently, creating a strong and cohesive visual identity. The brand guidelines also provided guidance on colours to be used in all print and online materials (such as templates and flyers).

Figure 3-RM ROADMAP logos and headers

Figure 4-RM ROADMAP colour palette

Crowdhelix developed Content Tracker for Dissemination and Communication Activities excel file to monitor and manage the project consortium's communication and dissemination activities. The consortium partners regularly updated the tracker. Similarly, Crowdhelix developed a form for RM-Roadmap Ambassadors for reporting engagement actions. These tracker forms have assisted Crowdhelix, project coordinators, and team members in monitoring all communication and dissemination activities planned and executed throughout the project duration. These included events, workshops, conferences, publications, social media posts, website updates, newsletters, press releases, etc.

In addition to monitoring targets and progress against project goals, tracker and forms have served as a central repository for documenting all dissemination outputs generated by the RM-Roadmap project. It has also ensured that materials produced, such as reports, articles, presentations, videos, and other materials, have been properly catalogued and are easily accessible to the project team for reference, reporting, and further distribution. The tracker and forms also have helped assess the impact of dissemination and communication activities by capturing metrics such as audience reach, engagement levels, media coverage and others. Tracker is structured around the following information: dissemination activities, publications,

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event planning and reporting summary.

5.4. RM Roadmap Website

A dedicated website (<https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>) was created and developed for the project on October 28th, 2022, as one of its main dissemination points. The website has been designed to act as a “living platform” and to evolve as the project reaches its various milestones, intending to engage with key players, and advocates. As the project matured, the website served to meet the evolving content needs of those audiences by having key messages updated and renewed. Care has been taken to ensure that the project’s social media channels can directly leverage any content published on the website. This has created a direct link between the website and its main distribution channels and provided the project’s social media accounts with the means to engage with the audiences outlined in D4.1. With respect to the formal project plan, this represents achieving Milestone 1 two months ahead of schedule. The RM-Roadmap Website homepage is shown below.

Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area

RM Roadmap is a pan-European community of research management excellence, coming together over three years to define a roadmap for our profession. A short description of the project and its objectives can be found in the [project workflow](#).

Follow our socials, sign up for updates or check back for news of our forthcoming

Figure 5 - RM-Roadmap Website Home Page

The website layout has been developed in line with the project’s visual identity and branding. Main menu items have been chosen as:

1. Home: Information about the project, results, links to the KCP, Ambassadors Network, project timeline, Project Team, information about the CARDEA project, and the contact information
2. Ambassadors: This section provides information about the network, a list of thematic and national ambassadors, Ambassador testimonials, and an FAQ
3. Community Connect: Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP)
4. Co-creation Results: Co-creation report, country reports and thematic reports
5. Project Workflow: objectives, partners, work packages and milestones information
6. Deliverables: All deliverables of the project
7. RM Roadmap Survey: Results and analysis of the RM Roadmap Survey
8. RM Professional Development Opportunities: The Dashboard and the catalogue of professional

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development opportunities for Research Managers in Europe

9. News & Events: Detailed information on RM-Roadmap news and events

Since its initiation in September 2022, the RM-Roadmap project website has had **90960 visits**. (as of 20 June 2025).

5.5. RM Roadmap Project Social Media Accounts

Social media has played an essential role in making our stakeholders aware of the RM ROADMAP project and highlighting the project’s progress. The project plan proposed that three social media channels would be established: Twitter/X, LinkedIn, and Facebook. Based on experience from the consortium partners' involvement with other Horizon actions, the consortium agreed that Facebook was no longer a worthwhile platform for RM-ROADMAP. As an alternative, a project home on ResearchGate was set up.

The @rmroadmap handle is secured on all three platforms:

- <https://x.com/RMROADMAP> (Operated by Crowdhelix) **422 followers (as of 20 June 2025)**
- www.linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap/ (Operated by Crowdhelix) **2475 followers (as of 20 June 2025)**
- www.researchgate.net/project/RM-ROADMAP (Operated by HETFA)

The account on the ResearchGate platform was closed due to a comparative lack of engagement. Below, a social media grid displays the rationale for the platforms on which RM ROADMAP have been active throughout the project.

Table 2- RM-Roadmap Social Media Grid

Media	Reasons
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active and wide base of professional stakeholders, and RM Professionals • Allowing various types of engagement
Twitter/X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active base of relevant stakeholders (i.e., other projects, research managers) • Effective for ‘live tweeting’ of events (i.e., plenary meetings, conferences) • Provides strong interaction and engagement with stakeholders thanks to retweets, tags, likes

During the RM-Roadmap project, various channels were utilised to engage with relevant accounts, foster a community of followers and enhance brand presence. These channels also served as tools for stakeholder and community engagement.

Crowdhelix created quarterly social media plans to coordinate and schedule different posts, enabling partners to highlight specific events, project outcomes, and collaboration opportunities. Implementing the

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project's social media plan has allowed RM-Roadmap to maintain consistent engagement with audiences, particularly on LinkedIn, resulting in a subject-specific following for the consortium. Below is an example of the quarterly social media plans prepared and managed by Crowdhelix, incorporating input and feedback from the consortium.

Publishing Date	Content	X Post	LinkedIn Post	Image/Graphic/Link/Script
Jan 2025 Week 1	Project TrainerLink	In support of the #RMROADMAP TrainerLink	Interested in Research Management? The RM-Roadmap	links in posts- Graphic from Ryan B.
Jan Week 2	Project Webinar	RM Roadmap Webinar presented by project partner	Interested in Research Management Funding Schem	links in posts- Graphic from Ryan B.
Jan Week 3	Funding/CARDEA	Interested in Research Management Funding Schem	Interested in Research Management Funding Schem	links in posts- Graphic from Ryan B.
Jan Week 4	NOVA/RMA Network/EARMA	The NOVA team will organize a workshop in the FINA	The NOVA team will organize a workshop in the FINA	links in posts- Graphic from Ryan B.
Jan Week 5	NOVA/RM Roadmap online session	In support of the #RMROADMAP TrainerLink	Interested in Research Management? The RM-Roadmap	links in posts- Graphic from Ryan B.
Feb 2025 Week 1	Online workshop promotion	Join us for our Online Workshop. The Added Value of	Join us for our Online Workshop. The Added Value of	links in posts- Graphic from Ryan B.
Feb Week 2	RM Framework project launch/EARMA	The RM Framework Project has launched on the 1st	The RM Framework Project has launched on the 1st	links in posts- Graphic from Ryan B.
Feb Week 3	Project database promotion	Efficient and focused networking is essential to the re	Efficient and focused networking is essential to the re	links in posts- Graphic from Ryan B.
Feb Week 4	RM Roadmap/Research Management Helix promotion	HRM Roadmap is the key project within the Crowdhelix	HRM Roadmap is the key project within the Crowdhelix	links in posts- Graphic from Ryan B.
Feb Week 4	RM Survey- Who are Research Managers?	The RM Roadmap survey shows that three c	The RM Roadmap survey shows that three c	Three quarter of Research Managers are women. TF Infographic from one-pager
March 2025 Week 1	Catalogue and Dashboard	What professional development opportunit	What professional development opportunities exist	Screenshot of the Catalogue & CARDEA Dashboard
March Week 2	Overall Numbers	Our RM mapping found 335 opportunities in	Looking for professional development as an RM?	Infographic with distribution of opportunities.
March Week 3	Training Formats	Training dominates RM professional develop	Did you know? Training dominates RM professional	Bar chart of training formats.
March Week 4	RM Survey- Where do Research Managers work?	Our survey shows that most of our Research	The RM survey reveals that most Research Manager	Infographic from one-pager
March Week 4	General assembly report back	TBC	TBC	TBC
April 2025 Week 1	Mobility challenges	Mobility for RMs is extremely limited! Only 21	Mobility for RMs is extremely limited! Only 2.69%	Infographic with distribution of opportunities.
April Week 2	Cost barriers	A staggering 69.23% of professional develop	Is RM training too expensive? A staggering 69.23%	Chart showing free vs. paid opportunities.
April Week 3	Career stage gaps	While 167 training programs (97.7%) are op	Does RM training match career needs? While 167	Chart of opportunities per RM stage
April Week 4	RM Survey- Education and Experience of Research Managers	Our survey reveals that Research Managers	The RM survey reveals that Research Managers are	Infographic from one-pager
May 2025 Week 1	EARMA event promotion	TBC	TBC	TBC
May Week 2	RM Network impacts	30.15% of all mapped opportunities come fr	RM Networks are shaping professional developm	Infographic with distribution of opportunities.
May Week 3	Geographical disparities	Western Europe has more structured RM tra	RM professional development isn't equally distrib	Map/ graph showing density of RM opportunities by co
May Week 4	RM Survey- Areas of Research Management	Our survey results show that several RMs a	The RM survey results show that Research Manager	Infographic from one-pager

Figure 6 - RM-Roadmap Social Media Plan (Jan-May 2025)

RM Roadmap LinkedIn Account

The RM ROADMAP LinkedIn account has been very active, gathering 2,475 followers from various professional fields across multiple European locations. The majority of the followers come from research, as well as project and programme management.

Figure 7 - RM-Roadmap LinkedIn Account

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In the last year alone, the account has garnered 62,354 impressions.

Metrics

Figure 8 -RM-Roadmap LinkedIn Account Impressions

Visitor metrics

Figure 9 -RM-Roadmap LinkedIn Account Visitor Metrics

The Visitor Metrics on LinkedIn evaluate traffic metrics for unique visitors and page views over time. Mobile metrics include LinkedIn native apps and mobile web browsers. Unique visitors are calculated daily and are not de-duplicated over multiple days.

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Follower demographics

Figure 10 - RM-Roadmap LinkedIn Account Follower Job Functions

Follower demographics

Figure 11- RM-Roadmap LinkedIn Account Follower Industry

The RM-Roadmap LinkedIn page has successfully attracted followers from the research and innovation ecosystem, targeting the project's primary audiences. Most of these followers come from the research, program and project management, and business development sectors. This targeted approach ensures that the project's communication and dissemination activities effectively reach the right audience.

The majority of followers are located in Portugal, Spain, Turkey, Belgium, the Netherlands, France, the United Kingdom, Italy, and Ireland. This distribution creates a balance between the locations of project

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partners and other European countries, including Widening Countries, as well as the locations of the RM-Roadmap Ambassadors.

Follower demographics

Figure 12 - RM-Roadmap LinkedIn Account Follower Location

RM Roadmap X (Twitter) Account

@RM ROADMAP has been mostly used to raise awareness about the project's progress, interact with key stakeholders, and build relationships with other Horizon Europe projects as well as to disseminate the project's news and current results. The account has 422 followers, and 177 tweets have been posted with 11.530 impressions to date.

Figure 13 -RM-Roadmap X/Twitter Account

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5.6. RM Roadmap Newsletters

Within the RM-Roadmap Project, CrowdHelix prepared and issued three newsletters in June 2024, March 2025 and June 2025. The RM-Roadmap Newsletters included information and news from the project, co-creation sessions, RM-Roadmap Mapping, Survey, Ambassadors Meetings, professional development opportunities, Research Management Helix, and activities organised by the consortium partners. The newsletters had 198 subscribers with an open rate of 46.9% for the first edition and 68% for the second edition.

Welcome to the inaugural issue of the RM Roadmap project newsletter, where we delve into the intricate world of research management and innovation across Europe. This newsletter is designed to keep you updated on our progress, insights, and breakthroughs in creating a robust framework for the European Research Area.

We follow a co-creation process that gather the existing communities and expand upon them on the project's Knowledge and Community Platform to reach two main objectives: create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap and inform the community about existing training, networking, funding and mobility opportunities.

The co-creation sessions aim to address challenges, identify best practices, and provide recommendations for training, networking, career development, and the overall recognition of research management as a distinct profession. The ultimate objective is to create a roadmap that can inform EU policy, support national research and innovation systems, and enhance the interoperability and consistency of research management practices across Europe. The co-creation sessions also aim to establish a robust framework that can support professional growth and collaboration across the European Union and associated countries for research managers.

Welcome to the second issue of the RM Roadmap project newsletter. This newsletter is designed to keep you updated on our progress, insights, and results as we strive to create a robust and useable framework for the European Research Area.

In this Newsletter:

1. Learn more about the Research Management Helix, where RM Roadmap is the key project: **Article 1**.
2. See key results from our Second Co-Creation Session: **Article 2**.
3. Explore our Catalogue of Existing Professional Development Opportunities: **Article 3**.
4. Find out more about our RM Roadmap Ambassadors Meeting, held 12-13 November: **Article 4**.
5. Read RM Roadmap Ambassador testimonials: **Article 5**.
6. See recent project activities and read about what is coming up.

[RM ROADMAP Website](#)

Figure 14 - RM-Roadmap Newsletters 1-2

5.7. RM Roadmap Press Releases

The following press releases were issued during the second reporting period of the RM ROADMAP Project.

27 Feb

Press Release: Europe’s Strategic Autonomy Agenda Requires Well-Resourced Research Management Professionals

Speaking at the launch of a report issued by the Horizon Europe-funded [RM Roadmap](#) project, Professor Kurt Deketelaere, Secretary General of the League of European Research Universities, said that research management professionals would require additional resources and funding if Europe is to promote its strategic Autonomy Agenda.

In a wide-ranging address, Professor Deketelaere touched on several subjects that intersected with ongoing discussions surrounding the European Union's next framework research programme - Framework Programme 10.

To maximise the potential of any new funding programme, Professor Deketelaere believes that the role played by research managers will need to be recognised and professionalised so that Europe can maximise its impact across numerous fields of science and research.

"It's not enough to have excellent researchers in our institutions. We need to have excellent research managers. I'm delighted that this has been recognised by the EU Commission".

"The strategic autonomy agenda will lead to a situation where there will be new research and innovation priorities, with new policies such as dual-use or export control or foreign interference".

"What does all that mean for open science, research integrity, academic freedom and institutional autonomy?"

"I expect that there will also be an increased amount of legal action from the Commission and Parliament because all legislation that is passed has an impact on research and universities, particularly around data management and AI".

Figure 15 - RM-Roadmap Press Release (February 2024)

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Member and partner news

RM Roadmap project seeks input on the landscape of research management in Europe

22 Apr 2024

The EU-funded project [RM Roadmap](#) recently launched a survey to get a comprehensive picture of the current situation of Research Managers (RMs) across Europe.

In the project's understanding, the term RMs covers a wide range of experts at different professional levels bearing specific knowledge:

- To streamline/facilitate the planning, the development, management, administration, communication and valorisation of research and innovation,
- To ensure compliance with policy objectives, funding programme requirements, financial rules and legal regulations,
- To improve the efficiency and effectiveness of R&I projects/system, and/or
- To enhance the impact of R&I on the society.

Whether they are generalists or specialised in a particular field, RMs are involved in different phases of the research and innovation projects/system.

Figure 16 - RM-Roadmap Press Release (April 2024)

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During the RM ROADMAP project, the consortium conducted various communication activities in addition to utilising the project's social media channels and website. A total of 55 communication activities were organised during both reporting periods. These included newsletter articles, social media posts, posters, flyers, press releases and announcements.

5.8. RM Roadmap Project Videos

The sixth video of the RM Roadmap was released in May 2024. It was the public session highlights of the 2nd RM Roadmap Ambassadors meeting hosted on EARMA's YouTube channel [here](#), and by the end of June 2025, it had 54 views.

5.9. Events

During RM-ROADMAP, three main events/event series were envisaged.

Table 3-RM ROADMAP envisaged main events

Event type	Description	Timing
RM-Roadmap Workshop	Ambassadors, invited key stakeholders and cluster project representatives will meet once per year (3 in total) for an update on RM-ROADMAP progress, strategic discussions and to receive training on moderating the KCP and advocating for RM-ROADMAP at national/ regional level	Annual
RM Helix event	Helix events are designed to generate discussion in the community of followers established on the Crowdhelix platform. A typical agenda features short briefs on exploitable results, pitches for new projects targeting open funding calls, and breakout discussions on emerging topics. The nature and objectives of each annual Helix event will be determined after the RM Helix is launched. Helix events may be virtual, or in person if co-located with another relevant Crowdhelix member event.	Annual – Physical or Virtual
RM-Roadmap final event	Conference to disseminate the results of RM-ROADMAP to stakeholders, including the project co-creation community, policy makers and partners engaging for further collaboration.	M34

RM Roadmap Ambassadors Meetings

1st Ambassadors Meeting (9 May 2023)

Recruitment of (National) Ambassadors was completed by 31 May 2023 (milestone 3). 115 ambassadors and associate ambassadors from 40 European countries were recruited. The selection of 35 thematic Ambassadors was completed in January 2024. The first RM Roadmap Ambassadors Meeting took place in Budapest, Hungary, May 9, 2023. The event commenced with a representative from HETFA, the host, Renáta Anna Jaksa, Head of the Division for International Cooperation addressing the attendees.

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The meeting highlighted the significance of research management in research and innovation ecosystem in Europe. The hybrid event was attended by representatives from the consortium partners, the plethora of the RM ROADMAP Ambassadors and national and European policy makers. In addition to 20 partners and 60 RM Roadmap ambassadors joining in Budapest, 108 joined online. Several ambassadors delivered presentations in Budapest showcasing their experiences and ideas in relation to engaging with local communities during and after the RM Roadmap project.

Figure 17 - Photos from the 1st Ambassadors Meeting in Prague, May 2023

A gender analysis conducted on of the ambassador’s network and found yielded the following breakdown: a) out of the 71 ambassadors, 43 are female, accounting for approximately 60.56% of the total ambassadors, b) out of the 44 associate ambassadors, 36 are female, making up approximately 81.82% of the total associate ambassadors. In addition, out of 35 thematic ambassadors, 29 are female, making up approximately 82.86% of the total thematic ambassadors. It should be noted that these numbers are based on a simplified gender analysis with the following limitations:

- This is a desk exercise based on available data from the call for ambassadors done by the project team.
- Ambassadors did not specify at application phase if they identified themselves with gender male or female.

Furthermore, for the simplicity of this analysis, we have not included a third gender option which constitutes another limitation per se.

2nd Ambassadors Meeting (13 March 2024)

The second Ambassador Meeting took place on March 13, 2024, in Lisbon, Portugal. The meeting started with welcoming notes from Hélder Lopes, the Director of Research and Innovation, and Diego Costa Pinto, the Vice-Dean for Research, both from the Universidad NOVA de Lisboa.

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The programme included a mix of plenary sessions, networking opportunities, and group work between ambassadors, providing further opportunities to learn from each other, create closer links, and share experiences. The speakers included Marc Mattis, Policy Officer at the European Commission from the Directorate General Research and Innovation, Nik Claesen, Managing Director of EARMA, Marilou Ramos Pamplona, Research Manager from the University of Liège, CARDEA Project.

The meeting was an excellent opportunity to come together and learn more about the current and future developments in European research management. It was also the first opportunity to meet the recently appointed thematic ambassadors and network with them to help them better integrate the project and become more aware of the following steps and how they can contribute. The event was also a renewed opportunity to liaise with colleagues from the CARDEA project and further develop the links with this sister project.

Figure 18 - Photo from the 2nd Ambassador Meeting in Lisbon, March 2024

3rd Ambassador Meeting (12-13 November 2024)

The 3rd RM Roadmap Ambassador Meeting took place on the 12th and 13th of November 2024 online as part of the EU-funded RM Roadmap project. The meeting started off with a presentation of the RM Competence Framework by Mary-Kate O'Regan, the coordinator of the CARDEA Project and was followed by a session showcasing the results of the RM Roadmap Project, including outcomes from the co-creation sessions, mapping exercise feeding into a catalogue mapping training, networking and mobility opportunities available to research managers in Europe; and the RM Roadmap Survey. The first day of the RM Roadmap Ambassador Meeting was open to the public, with about 111 attendees. The second day of the 3rd RM Roadmap Ambassador Meeting included discussions on the upcoming co-creation session to commence on the 14th of November until the 19th of December 2024 on the topic of the Career Development Framework.

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Figure 19 - Photo of the 3rd Ambassador Meeting Online, November 2024

The Final Event (24th of June 2025)

The final event had 65 participants from 23 countries including RM Roadmap partners, RM Roadmap ambassadors, RM Roadmap advisory board members and other stakeholders. The Meeting started off with a session on the engagement of ambassadors, highlighting the work or the RM Roadmap ambassadors and their mission. The event then continued with the discussion of the overarching roadmap as the final goal of the RM Roadmap project. Furthermore, an interactive session in the form of discussion groups on topics including a career framework, skills and competencies of research managers, the overarching roadmap, career development and the recognition of research managers was engaging all participants in lively discussions. The meeting then ended with a call to action discussing the future of RM Roadmap and its outcomes, including the sustainability of the RM Roadmap ambassador network.

Research Management Helix Events

Within the RM Roadmap project, Crowdhelix organised three Helix Events to promote the virtual community and the project. Annual Research Management Helix Events were designed and delivered to generate discussion in the community of followers established on the Crowdhelix platform. Each RM Helix Event focused on different topics relevant to the community such as the role of research management professionals across the ERA and recognition and professionalisation of the RM.

First Research Management Helix Event (24 April 2023)

The Research Management Helix was launched at the 2023 EARMA Conference with great success. The Research Management (RM) Helix was officially launched in month 8 of the RM ROADMAP project on the Crowdhelix platform at EARMA’s annual international conference in Prague, April 2023, with over 1300 participants (see the corresponding digital leaflet in A.1 Annex 1).

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Figure 20 - Launch of the RM Helix, at the EARMA 2023 Conference in Prague

Figure 21-Material for promoting the Research Management Helix, at the launch of the Helix, at the EARMA 2023 conference in Prague

Second Research Management Helix Event (26 February 2024)

Crowdhelix and EARMA organised the second Helix event titled “Navigating the Research Management Landscape: Insights from Europe” on 26 February 2024. The event was organised online with the participation of 150 researchers/research managers across Europe. The event explored the role of research management professionals across the European Research Area. The speakers included: Michael Browne, CEO, Crowdhelix, Nik Claesen, Managing Director, EARMA and Kurt Deketelaere, SG LERU. The presentations focused on the importance of research and innovation management across the ERA, RM Roadmap Co-creation Process and Key Exploitable Results & RM Roadmap Research Management Helix.

Leaning on the latest results from the Horizon Europe-funded RM Roadmap project the event addressed national networks and associations available to research managers and the broader landscape in which they are engaged. The RM Roadmap project collated its findings from the first co-creation session in the largest collaboration between Europe’s Research Management networks ever to take place.

The event recording can be found [here](#).

Figure 22 - Second Research Management Helix Event Poster

Third Research Management Helix Event (27 February 2025)

The last Helix event of the RM Roadmap project, titled “Momentum in Research Management: Pathways to Recognition,” was organised in collaboration with Crowdhelix and EARMA on 27 February 2025 as an online event. 80 participants from the scientific community, industry, policy makers, and the general public attended the event. The speakers included: Michael Browne, CEO, Crowdhelix, Nik Claesen, Managing Director, EARMA

The event focused on several key topics aimed at enhancing the role and recognition of research managers within the European Research Area (ERA). Discussions highlighted concrete steps being taken at the EU level to solidify this recognition and professionalization, including the introduction of the RM Comp, a Skills and Competency Framework for Research Managers. Participants also explored the next steps at the EU level and

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the supporting projects like the RM Roadmap, CARDEA, and the RM Framework. A significant emphasis was placed on working towards accreditation and establishing clear career pathways for research management professionals, ensuring their critical contributions are acknowledged and developed within the research landscape. The event recording can be found [here](#).

Figure 23 - 3rd Research Management Helix Event Poster

Figure 24 - Screenshot from the 3rd Research Management Helix Event

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The Final Event (24th of June 2025)

The final event had 65 participants from 23 countries including RM Roadmap partners, RM Roadmap ambassadors, RM Roadmap advisory board members and other stakeholders. The Meeting started off with a session on the engagement of ambassadors, highlighting the work of the RM Roadmap ambassadors and their mission. The event then continued with the discussion of the overarching roadmap as the final goal of the RM Roadmap project. Furthermore, an interactive session in the form of discussion groups on topics including a career framework, skills and competencies of research managers, the overarching roadmap, career development and the recognition of research managers was engaging all participants in lively discussions. The meeting then ended with a call to action discussing the future of RM Roadmap and its outcomes, including the sustainability of the RM Roadmap ambassador network.

The event agenda can be reached at:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1eCutmWJSv8mQK4CZ349aWjKMWYv9tEUm/view?usp=sharing>

Figure 25- RMROADMAP Consortium at the Final Dissemination Event

Workshops and conference organisation and/or participation of RM Roadmap partners promoting and/or presenting RM-Roadmap Project

Throughout the project, the consortium actively participated in various international research management conferences, seminars, and workshops, where they presented the RM-Roadmap to diverse audiences. These audiences included members of the scientific community (higher education and research), the general public, research managers from universities and research institutions, national research management associations, as well as young and potential research managers. The consortium effectively networked and engaged with relevant stakeholders by sharing the core objectives and outcomes of the RM-Roadmap.

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Below is a list of events that the consortium organised or contributed to in order to disseminate information about the RM-Roadmap Project during the second reporting period. In total, 73 events were attended or organised, reaching over 4,500 participants.

Table 4 - List of Dissemination Activities

No	Lead Partner	Dissemination Type	Title	Date	Location	Link (if available)
1	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	Utrecht Annual Conference for Research Management- Online	13-Sept-2023	Online	
2	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	BE- Arma Event- Brussels	15-Sept-23	Brussels, Belgium	https://bearma.be/files/2023-09-15%20LiveEvent%20Workshop.pdf
3	HETFFA	Participation to a Conference	Drive impactful collaboration: Bridging BESTPRAC & EARMAimpact	18-20 Sept 23	Ljubljana, Slovenia	https://earma.org/conferences/impact-bestprac-joint-meeting/
4	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	ARMA-NL Conference	28-29-Sep-23	Lunteren, Netherlands	https://armanl.eu/events/arma-nl-1st-annual-conference/
5	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	EARMA Strategy Meeting Krakow	2-Oct-23	Krakow, Poland	
6	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	Opening Conference of the V4+WB RMA Network Project	17-18 Oct-23	Bratislava, Slovakia	https://opusproject.eu/openscience-news/opening-conference-of-the-v4wb-rma-network-project-advancing-research-management-and-administration-in-the-v4wb-region-2/
7	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	Swedish Association of Research Managers and Administrators (SWARMA) Brussels	26-Oct-23	Brussels, Belgium	
8	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	Spanish Representation- Brussels	26-Oct-23	Brussels, Belgium	
9	EARMA	Participation to a	Action 17 Workshop- Barcelona	8-Nov-23	Barcelona, Spain	

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		Conference				
10	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	V4 Training- Brussels	10-Nov-23	Brussels, Belgium	
11	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	AI Day	10-Nov-23		
12	HETFA	Training	Training for the RMs and researchers of the Hungarian Research Network	13-Nov-23	Budapest, Hungary	
13	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	Leadership Event	22-Nov-23		
14	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	12th Meeting of ERION and 1st Open Science Meeting	21-22-Nov-23	Brussels, Belgium	https://earma.org/conferences/open-science-meeting/
15	HETFA	Participation to a Conference	Where are the trends of the European Research Area pointing? Professional support for Hungarian research excellence	28-Nov-23	Budapest, Hungary	https://nkfih.gov.hu/hivatalrendezvenyei/merre-mutatnak-europai-kutatasi-terseg-trendjei
16	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	EAIC meeting	13-Dec-23		
17	EARMA HETFA	Organisation of a Workshop	The Past, Present And Future Of Professional Development Of Research Management	16-Jan-24	Digital EARMA Event	https://earma.org/conferences/past-present-and-future-professional-development-research-management/
18	CYI	Participation to a workshop	TWIN4MERIT Cyprus R&I Stakeholders Meeting	23-Jan-24	Nicosia, Cyprus	
19	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	European Research Manager- Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	23-Feb-24	Madrid, Spain	
20	CHX EARMA	Organisation of a Workshop	Navigating the Research Management Landscape: Insights from Europe	26-Feb-24	Digital CHX Event	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B_bVA2jKNZg
21	EARMA	Participation	Leadership event	26-28-	Brussels,	

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		to a Conference		Feb-24	Belgium	
22	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	AI Day	29-Feb-24	Brussels, Belgium	
23	EARMA HETFA	Participation to a Conference	Raising Excellence in Research and Project Management and Administration through Close Cooperation - International REX RMA Closing Conference -	5-Mar-24	Bratislava, Slovakia	https://rex-rma.stuba.sk/en/tag/conference/
24	NOVA	Organisation of a Conference	2nd Ambassador Meeting Lisbon	13-Mar-24	Lisbon, Portugal	https://www.rmroadmap.eu/news-events/wnllac60li7w76668rhrd6fogyf8x
5	HETFA	Participation to a Conference	Hungarian Research Management Meetup	20-Mar-24	Budapest, Hungary	https://www.horizonteuropa.nkfi.gov.hu/hivatalrol/hivatalrendezvenyei/2-kutatasmenedzsment-szakmai-nap?objectParentFolderId=20633
26	CYI	Participation to a workshop	Focus Group	12-April-24	Nicosia, Cyprus	
27	EARMA HETFA CHX	Organisation of a Conference	Odense EARMA Conference	23-25-Apr-24	Odense, Denmark	https://earma.org/conferences/earma-conference-odense-2024/
28	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	13th ERION EARMA Thematic Group Event	15-May-24	Brussels, Belgium	https://earma.org/conferences/13th-erion-earma-thematic-group-event/
29	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	Prague Charles University International Advisory Board	16-May-24	Prague, Czechia	
30	HETFA	Participation to a Conference	Training School (V4WB RMA Network Plus Project)	15-16-May-24	Banja Luka, Bosnia & Herzegovina	https://www.euraxess.me/montenegro/news/call-applications-v4wb-rma-network-plus-training-school-

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						banja-luka
31	NOVA	Participation to a Conference	Encontro de Ciência 2024	3-5-Jul-24	Porto, Portugal	https://www.encontrociencia.pt/noticia/encontro-ciencia-2024-o-balanco/
32	EARMA	Organisation of a Workshop	2nd Open Science Thematic Group Meeting- Brussels	18-19-Sep-24	Brussels, Belgium	https://earma.org/conferences/2nd-open-science-earma-thematic-group-event/
33	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	2024 SRAI Annual Meeting	26-Oct-24	Chicago, USA	https://www.srainternational.org/events/event-description?CalendarEventKey=d842a112-61b8-4148-ac51-018e40529ce4&Home=%2Fevents%2Fcalendar
34	EARMA	Organisation of a Workshop	14th ERION EARMA Thematic Group event	30-Oct-24	Barcelona, Spain	https://earma.org/conferences/14th-erion-earma-thematic-group-event/
35	CYI	Participation to a workshop	A Career in Research Management	30-Oct-24	Online event	
36	EARMA all partners	Organisation of a Workshop	3rd RM Roadmap Ambassador Meeting	12-13-Nov-25	Digital EARMA Event	https://www.rmroadmap.eu/news-events/3rd-rm-roadmap-ambassador-meeting
37	EARMA	Participation to a workshop	Synergies of Impact: Crafting Proposals and Building Institutional Culture	27-Nov-24	Brussels, Belgium	https://earma.org/conferences/earmaimpact-training/
38	CHX	Organisation of a Workshop	Elevating Research Management Skills: Frameworks and Resources	5-Dec-24	Digital CHX Event	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NCKVuNHE-uA
39	CHX	Organisation of a Workshop	Momentum in Research Management: Pathways to Recognition	27-Feb-25	Digital CHX Event	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3fsWdj9Bapc
40	EARMA	Organisation of a	CATALISI General Assembly	21-Jan-25		

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		Workshop				
41	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	FINAL CONFERENCE OF THE V4+WB RMA NETWORK PROJECT - Budapest	24-Jan-25	Budapest, Hungary	https://hetfa.eu/2025/01/final-conference-of-the-v4wb-rma-network-plus-project/
42	EARMA HETFA	Organisation of a Workshop	RM Framework: Advancing Research Management Training Across Europe Kick-off Meeting	11-Feb-25	Brussels, Belgium	https://earma.org/news/rm-framework-advancing-research-management-training-across-europe/
43	HETFA	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Presentation to Hungarian Research Project Managers at the University of Veterinary Medicine, Budapest	18-Feb-25	Budapest, Hungary	
44	NOVA	Organisation of an event	LS4FUTURE Career Development - presenting findings of the RM Roadmap project, together with insights on CARDEA project and ERA Action 17	27-Feb-25	Online	
45	HETFA	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Study trip for Czech Research Project Managers organised by CZELO office	12-Mar-25	Brussels, Belgium	
46	NOVA	Participation in a training event	EUTOPIA Health Research Managers Training Programme	14-16-Apr-25	Lisbon, Portugal	
47	HETFA	Participation to a Conference	V4 Research Project Managers Training	28-30-Apr-25	Brussels, Belgium	
48	HETFA	Participation to a Conference	inorms - RM Roadmap session: Insights on Research Managers in Europe, WP1 results	6-May-25	Madrid, Spain	
49	EARMA all partners	Organisation of a Workshop	INORMS 2025	8-May-25	Madrid, Spain	https://earma.org/conferences/inorms-congress-madrid-2025/programme/

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50	NOVA		Re-Data Webinar: Profiles and Competences in Research Management and Open Data	16-May-2025	Online	
51	EARMA	Organisation of a Conference	RM-Roadmap Final Event	24-Jun-2025	Brussels, Belgium	

RM Roadmap Ambassadors have been actively reporting on various engagement activities they have led, organised, co-organised, or presented in connection with the RM Roadmap project. So far, they have reported a total of 64 engagement activities, both online and in-person, at various events. These efforts have reached over 3,250 participants, including members of the scientific community and research management professionals from Albania, Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, Finland, Ireland, Kosovo, Latvia, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Norway, Romania, Switzerland, Slovenia, Spain, and Türkiye.

6. Clustering Activities

6.1. The Research Management Helix

CrowdHelix is a pan-European Open Innovation Network that connects and enables research organisations, SMEs and industry to collaborate, innovate and grow. The Network has more than 799 member organisations from 57 countries and is present in all EU Member State countries.

The Network is set-up around thematic areas called “Helixes” and is supported by a technology platform (<https://www.crowdHelix.com/>), where these virtual communities are hosted. A Helix is a specialised community/cluster comprising experts and research and innovation professionals across research management, academia and industry. The CrowdHelix platform consists of multiple thematic helixes (50+), whose reach extends to 500,000+ research and innovation actors (across its members), and directly to more than 12000 users currently on the CrowdHelix platform.

The CrowdHelix platform facilitates connection between various types of stakeholders sharing common interests via the opportunities posted under up to three themed Helixes. It provides the following main functionalities:

- Announcements
- Collaboration opportunities posting
- Expertise offer
- Interaction with experts/organisations
- Results (at various levels of TRLs as well as best practices, policy papers and trainings).

Interested parties can contact the authors via public or private messages. The platform users can also engage proactively by using the search tool - which is refined by opportunities (posts), organisations, groups (“sub-organisations”), or experts (users) - to contact potential partners directly.

The **Research Management Helix**, hosted on the CrowdHelix Open Innovation platform, has played and continues to play a primary role in disseminating the projects’ KERs, providing robust support for the dissemination and communication activities of the RM ROADMAP project, serving as an engine for impact, exploitation, and clustering activities.

The Research Management Helix is led and managed by CrowdHelix on the CrowdHelix open innovation platform. CrowdHelix has been tasked with maintaining an active community while the consortium members were responsible for scientific direction of the Helix.

The RM Helix has been used as:

- A tool to accelerate and promote the dissemination of the RM ROADMAP project
- A repository to publish and promote the Key Exploitable Results coming from the RM ROADMAP
- A platform for facilitating matchmaking and clustering activities
- A platform to connect with people, collaborate and create partnerships
- A virtual community where organisations can subscribe and connect with other stakeholders

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- A tool to make posts for upcoming funding opportunities, events, workshops, and vacancies
- A tool for profiling and connecting innovation to global end-users using a recommender engine

Helix benefits from the existing wider Crowdhelix network (799+ member organisations from 57 countries incl. all EU Member States) and has the potential to reach 18,000+ research and innovation collaborators in more than 50 virtual thematic areas/clusters, which cover most research and innovation fields.

Research Management Helix is an international Open Innovation community of RM practitioners, specialists, other stakeholders, relevant policy makers, and citizen interest groups. In addition to facilitating opportunities that can further progress the RM domain of practice, Helix has been supporting the RM Roadmap by accelerating community development and translation of project results into cross-sectoral impact across the European Research Area and beyond.

Over the course of the project, the Research Management Helix has grown into a thriving virtual community with over **1020 experts from 358 member organisations across 77 countries**. **RM Helix users shared over 95 posts** aimed at establishing consortia for new proposals, sharing ongoing project results, and promoting events, training sessions, and other related activities.

Research Management
Co-creating the future of Research Management, bringing our community together to define & support the profession

Background
Globalisation of research, complexity of funding and increasing transnational collaboration and mobility has been mirrored in the evolution of research management (RM). Virtually every research-active university and organisation now has a RM function, whether nascent or mature. Recognising that investing in research and innovation is, in essence, an investment in a sustainable future, many organisations are creating new modes of research office, who may provide support to individual researchers while representing strategic research programme objectives.

Variation in skillset, functions, capacity, and capabilities of RMs varies greatly, as does the national context in which they operate. However, key stakeholders including most funding bodies, now recognize that RM is developing into a truly global profession, with a growing necessity for skills, shared practices and professional networks. RM extends beyond universities, and its practitioners are found within funding bodies, charities, foundations, government, and industry.

Key Project: RM ROADMAP
RM ROADMAP (Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area) will create a roadmap for the future of research management (RM) in Europe and a community to support the delivery of that roadmap. Coordinated by EARMA, RM ROADMAP will connect existing European networks on a smart community platform which will enable an unprecedented co-creation process of RM in the world.

The RM ROADMAP collaborators believe that investment in the RM community will facilitate and accelerate research results reaching the market and thereby the real economy. The project aims to (1) create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap, and (2) inform the community about the existing training, networking, funding, and mobility opportunities. RM ROADMAP is supported by a pan-European network of RMs, supporting the establishment of strategic, cross-border partnerships between RMs in industry, Research Funding Organisations, higher education, and research institutions – never seen before at such a scale.

The results of the 1st Co-Creation Session of RM ROADMAP show that the community informs RM ROADMAP of the need for support from government bodies and funding agencies to establish and sustain support research management networks and associations to bring about recognition of the profession. The report from the first Co-Creation Session of the RM ROADMAP: "Understanding the landscape: National Networks and Associations" can be found in the Helix Resources on this page.

Research Management Helix
This Helix is an international Open Innovation community of RM practitioners, specialists, and other stakeholders, as well as relevant policy makers and citizen interest groups. In addition to facilitating opportunities that can further progress the RM domain of practice, the Helix will support RM-Roadmap by accelerating community development and translation of project results into cross-sectoral impact across the European Research Area and beyond.

Seeking collaborators for Research Management projects?
Post a new Opportunity in this Helix

1064 Experts

363 Organisations

78 Countries

RM ROADMAP Overview

Michael Browne
Helix Leader

Organisations
European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA)
Leading Organisation

Projects
RM ROADMAP
Key Project

Figure 26 - Landing Page of the Research Management Helix on the Crowdhelix Open Innovation Platform

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The Crowdhelix Open Innovation Platform has an existing 18000 users, who are automatically notified upon the creation of a Helix. This means that the Crowdhelix users have access to all the posts, including the Research Management posts. Some opportunities also address cross-cutting topics, which may include up to three helixes. The Research Management Helix acts as a resource tool with links to the project website, social media and any Dissemination and Communication activities produced during the project.

The Helix contains information about the project, a list of the project members, and a resources tool with links to the project website and social media sites, and dissemination and communication materials (i.e. presentations, scientific publications, videos) produced during the project (by partner request). Partners will be requested to select and send these materials to the helix manager and ask him/her to promote them. The stakeholders will be notified by the platform about the advancements of RM ROADMAP project, with the aim of maximising the visibility of the results to actors best placed to make use of them.

Figure 27 - Percentage of RM Helix membership from Widening Countries vs Non-widening Countries

The figure above shows the proportion of member organisations in the Research Management Helix, including those from widening countries and other European nations at the end of the project. A total of 105 organisations from widening countries and 251 organisations from non-widening European countries and other regions are represented in the Helix. The geographical distribution of the Research Management Helix users is shown in the figure below. RM Helix has members from Europe, Asia, Africa, North and South America, and Oceania, demonstrating the reach of the community beyond the EU to a global scene.

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

Figure 28-Location of Research Management Helix Users

The structure of the organisations within the Research Management Helix aligns with the target groups identified in the Project. These groups include Research and Technology Organisations, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), corporations, and relevant associations and specialist organisations.

Figure 29-Typology of RM Helix Member Organisations

Furthermore, the job titles among the Research Management Helix users correspond to the project's audience. Below are examples of various categories and job titles held by users of the Research Management Helix.

- Research and Academic Leadership:** Professor, Associate Professor, Assistant Professor, Lecturer, Senior Lecturer, Dean, Principal Investigator, Vice-President, Senior Researcher

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

- **Research Management and Support:** Research Manager, Research Project Manager, Project Manager, Research Development Officer, Research Funding Specialist, Grant Writer, Funding Officer, International Projects Expert, Grant Advisor, Programme Manager, Research Integrity & Compliance Officer, Impact Acceleration Manager
- **Senior Management and Executive Leadership:** CEO, Director of Research, Development & Innovation, Executive Director, Executive Manager, CFO, Managing Coordinator, General Manager, Chairman of the Managing Board, Managing Partner, Head of Research Management, Head of Business Development, Head of Technology Transfer Office, Head of External Engagement Office
- **Innovation, Technology Transfer and Business Development:** Innovation and Research Advisor, Business Development and Innovation Manager, Business Analyst, R&D Manager, Global Network Manager

These categorised stakeholder groups reflect the RM Helix community's objective of creating an ecosystem focused on the RM domain, fostering community growth, influencing policy, and translating project results into impactful outcomes.

As a hub for research management professionals and experts, Research Management Helix is closely aligned with all Helixes on the Crowdhelix platform. These include **Helixes related to Horizon Europe Clusters**, (Health, Culture, Creativity and Society, Security, Digital, Climate, Energy, and Mobility, Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment), **Helixes related to Horizon Europe Missions** (Mission Cancer, Mission Climate, Smart Cities, Mission Ocean & Waters, Mission Soil), **Helixes related to funded Horizon European Projects** (such as Pancreatic Cancer, Smart Medtech, Hydrogen, Printed Electronics, Trustworthy AI) and **Helixes related to cross cutting issues** such as Open Science and Excellent Science.

Figure 30 - Aligned Helixes on Crowdhelix Platform

Crowdhelix's recommender engine, which is embedded within all Helixes, holds significant value for the RM ROADMAP Project. This AI-powered matchmaking algorithm seamlessly connects posted opportunities with organisations and individuals possessing the required expertise. When an organisation or platform user registers on the Helix and highlights their areas of expertise, the platform's recommender engine assists in identifying suitable opportunities within the Helix. This matchmaking algorithm can also facilitate connections with various stakeholders and aid in finding specific collaborators to meet the project's needs.

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

Registered members of the Research Management Helix have access to the following main functionalities:

- posting collaboration opportunities for new proposals and ongoing projects.
- offering their expertise to join consortia.
- capability to interact with experts in other organisations.
- posting research outputs and results to accelerate RM ROADMAP's and other projects' impact.
- participating in events organised by the Helix

The following are recent opportunity posts on the Research Management Helix. These posts focus on various initiatives, including the formation of consortia, sharing of expertise, searching for partners with specific areas of expertise, offers for hosting MSCA fellowships, opportunities arising from ongoing projects, and the dissemination of events. Along with collaboration opportunities, the Research Management Helix also shares various research outputs and results from EU-funded projects, as well as research funded by institutions or regional and national sources. Key exploitable results from the RM ROADMAP project have been featured on the results page of the Helix.

The screenshot displays eight posts on the Research Management Helix results page. Each post is a card with a title, a brief description, and a 'Funded by the European Union' badge. The posts are:

- European Policy Brief: A Roadmap for Research Management (RM) to Strengthen the European Research Area (ERA)** (CrowdHelix)
- Report from the 2nd co-creation session of the RM Roadmap project: Who are Research Managers / Skills and Competences** (CrowdHelix)
- Catalogue of existing professional development opportunities** (CrowdHelix)
- Report from the 1st RM ROADMAP co-creation session on understanding the landscape on national networks** (CrowdHelix)
- Case study: Professionalizing Research Management in Catalonia** (Universidad Politecnica de Madrid)
- SHAPE-ID Toolkit for Inter- and Transdisciplinary Research: Quick Guide for Pre-Award RMAs** (Trinity College Dublin)
- Position paper: The past, present, and future of the European R&I Framework Programmes 2014-2027** (European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA))
- Online Research Management learning resources & self-development tool** (HETFA Kutatóintézet Kft.)

Figure 31 - Results Shared on the Research Management Helix

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The Research Management Helix has been populated by contributions from each project member since its launch and the content corresponds to the Helix Roadmap - a guiding plan built in collaboration with the partners and according to the needs of the project.

The screenshot displays a grid of collaboration opportunities on the Research Management Helix platform. Each card includes a profile picture and name of the user, their affiliations, and details of the opportunity. The opportunities include:

- Career Opportunity - Senior Post-Doctoral Researcher/Post-Doctoral Researcher Centre for Gerontology and Rehabilitation:** Seeking a Visiting Researcher with expertise in Rehabilitation, Gerontology, and Advanced dementia.
- Training opportunity for Research Managers: Research Management Certification Program:** Seeking a Research manager with expertise in Research management and administration.
- Join the RM ROADMAP project for an engaging session at the INORMS Congress (May 8, 2025, from 11:00 to 12:00 in Room Amsterdam):** Seeking a Research management professional.
- Seeking evaluators for MSCA COFUND project CHARLESTON:** Seeking an Evaluator with expertise in Sdg and Building sustainability.
- MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2025: Hosting Offers at Vilnius University:** Seeking an Existing Project with expertise in MscA, Phd, and Marie curie fellowships.
- Join Our Exclusive Athens 2025: Advanced EU Funding & Project Innovation Camp:** Seeking a Project Participant or Event Attendee with expertise in Research & innovation.
- Framework Programme 10: Preparing for EU Research and Innovation Funding Beyond 2027 - Event recording now available:** Seeking an Existing Project with expertise in Eu funding and Horizon europe.
- Seeking for Erasmus+ Project Partner:** Seeking a Work Package Leader or Consortium Partner with expertise in Research management, Ai, and Technology transfer.

Figure 32 - Recent Collaboration Opportunities on the Research Management Helix

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Figure 33 - Research Management Helix Roadmap

In the first phase of the Roadmap, Research Management Helix was successfully relaunched. Crowdhelix onboarded all partners, the consortium engaged stakeholders and built connections with sister projects. In the second phase, Helix activities concentrated on expanding the network and enhancing stakeholder engagement. This included targeted communications, clustering activities with sister projects such as CARDEA, exploring funding opportunities, and disseminating KERs as focus areas. As part of the RM ROADMAP Project, Crowdhelix has organised three Helix Events, further explained in the events section.

To ensure project sustainability, the Research Management Helix will be maintained for five years free of charge after the project ends. The main objective is to have the Research Management Helix as a self-sustaining community committed to facilitating collaborative partnerships.

The RM Helix was expected to attract 150 stakeholders to join the Helix, engaging with the RM ROADMAP project by M36. As a result of the wide dissemination and engagement of RM ROADMAP, the RM Helix has surpassed the KPIs set at the proposal stage of the project and hosts over 1012 users from 356 organisations across 76 countries by the end of M34. As the Helix will remain operational for five years following the end of the Project, the Helix is expected to attract more users and organisations, solidifying its presence as a collaboration community for research managers.

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6.2. Activities with other EU projects and initiatives

Clusters, in the context of Horizon Europe, consist of related projects and initiatives with similar thematic focus and inter-dependent research activities that come together in common actions, events or meetings and share concepts, ideas and problems as well as communication and dissemination activities. With respect to DCE, the primary project-project relationship to be established is with RM-ROADMAP's 'sister' project funded on the same call [HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-20], "CARDEA". Both consortia have shared a willingness to collaborate where synergies exist and have engaged in continuous collaboration and exchange of information through both projects' activities. RM ROADMAP has linked to Cardea's website on RM ROADMAP's home page with relevant links and information.

Joint Efforts for Strengthening Research Management in the European Research Area

Further to RM Roadmap (Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area), the other EU project funded towards the Europe-wide scheme for research managers is [CARDEA – Career Acknowledgement for Research \(Managers\) Delivering for the European Area](#). Collaboration between the two projects will maximise impact.

Figure 34 - Promotion of the CARDEA Project on the Homepage of RM ROADMAP Website

Both projects have also linked each other's tools and websites. The dashboard, developed as a joint activity between the CARDEA and the RM-ROADMAP projects, can be found on each project's website as shown in the figures below.

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Figure 35 - Dashboard on the CARDEA Project Website

Figure 36 - Dashboard on the RM-ROADMAP Website

RM-ROADMAP and CARDEA Project have also collaborated in joint events and activities, which are presented below.

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RM-ROADMAP Ambassadors Meetings

Representatives of CARDEA project participated in the 1st RM ROADMAP Ambassadors meeting between 9-10 May 2023 and discussed Career Acknowledgement for Research Managers Delivering for the European Area. This presentation looked at the preliminary findings of the CARDEA research and the socio-economic profile of a research manager that these results have discovered.

Figure 37 - Professor Longo Eduard Balbuena Longo, CERCA and representative

Marilou Ramos Pamplona, Research Manager at the University of Liege and CARDEA representative presented the more recent developments in the project during the panel discussion at the 2nd RM ROADMAP Ambassadors meeting on March 13, 2024.

Figure 38 - The 2nd RM-ROADMAP Ambassadors Meeting

Mary-Kate O'Regan, CARDEA Coordinator and HR Business Manager at the University College Cork, presented the RM Competence Framework at the 3rd Ambassadors Meeting organised between 12-13 November 2024.

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Figure 39 - The 3rd RM-ROADMAP Ambassadors Meeting

Furthermore, RM-ROADMAP project and consortium was represented in activities organised by the CARDEA Project as outlined below.

CARDEA ACADEMY - Career Framework for Research Managers - 25th September 2023

As part of the CARDEA Academy, Virág Zsár, Senior Grant Advisor, HETFA Research Institute presented a talk on the definition of research management during the CARDEA Academy organised on 25 September 2023 in collaboration with the CARDEA project. Over 160 people participated in the event and both projects organised focus groups for collecting feedback.

Figure 40 - RM-ROADMAP Project Presentation at CARDEA Academy

CROWDHELIX Training Event

Crowdhelix organised a clustering event with the CARDEA project on December 5, 2024. Michael Browne, CEO, Crowdhelix and Cais Jurgens, Head of Membership Development presented RM ROADMAP Project and Research Management Helix while Mary-Kate O’Regan, CARDEA Coordinator and HR Business Manager at the University College Cork, presented new tools developed by the CARDEA project which have been informed by the results of the CARDEA Survey and have been designed to support Research Managers across

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

the European Research Area. In total 76 participants joined the event and were informed about both projects.

Figure 41 - RM ROADMAP/CARDEA Clustering Event

In addition to the CARDEA Project, the RM-Roadmap Project has also started collaborating with the newly launched RM Framework Project. RM Framework aims to support the development of a European qualification system for Research Management by standardising educational and training programmes and elaborating a quality label to enhance interoperability and improve the RM profession within the European Research Area. RM-ROADMAP Project coordinator EARMA is coordinating the RM Framework project while, RM ROADMAP partner, HETFA is among the consortium members of the project. Both RM-Roadmap and RM-Framework projects are co-branding. Following the end of the RM-ROADMAP project, Crowdhelix will hand over the LinkedIn account for RM-Roadmap to the RM-Framework partners to maintain the community engagement and awareness achieved by the RM-Roadmap project.

Figure 42 - RM Roadmap & RM Framework Co-branding

7. Conclusions

The RM ROADMAP Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report (D4.6) summarises the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities of the project for the 36 months of the project. The report summaries different activities and impact created through DCE activities in the project.

The Website of the RM ROADMAP project has had over 90000 visits since its launch and the project social media accounts (LinkedIn and X) have had more than 120000 social media impressions and over 2000 followers.

Launched in April 2023, the Research Management Helix has grown into an active virtual collaboration community with 1064 users and 363 organisations across 78 countries. A total of three Helix events were organised to promote the virtual community and the project and these events attracted over 200 participants and further connected the RM ROADMAP project to other initiatives such as the CARDEA project.

Throughout the project, three RM ROADMAP Ambassadors meetings online and in-person. RM ROADMAP has 115 ambassadors from 40 countries that led the onboarding of the RM Community to the Knowledge and Communication Platform.

The Consortium has successfully promoted RM ROADMAP on many other channels, including the Research Professional News, EARMA, EUA, and HETFA websites well as through the Crowdhelix platform, the networks BESTPRAC, ASTP, KOWI etc. and through national networks in dedicated events such as those of DARMA, NARMA, etc. This was partly achieved through the participation and/or organisation of different events such as international and national conferences and workshops e.g., EARMA 2023, EARMA 2024, INORMS 2023, INORMS 2025 etc.

RM ROADMAP's Communication Plan presents the different activities with the purpose of informing about the project but also its main results and impacts. Throughout the project timeframe, RM ROADMAP communication and dissemination activities have been timely, accurate and coordinated to address the right audiences. The different actions were correctly tailored to target the different audience segments to inform about the project and bring the community together. These can be demonstrated by the KPIs reached in 36 months of implementation. This demonstrates the dedication of the RM ROADMAP Consortium to the project's objectives and ERA Action 17, i.e. to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the European Union (EU), including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

8. Annexes

Annex 1 Joining the RM Helix Dissemination Leaflet

Funded by the European Union

RESEARCH MANAGEMENT HELIX

www.rmroadmap.eu

What is the Research Management Helix?

The Research Management Helix is an online community where research managers can share ideas, knowledge and best practice.

Who is it for?

Anybody involved in research management activities. We recognise that research managers have a broad range of specialisms and we want to create a space where they can share knowledge and experiences.

Why join?

The Research Management Helix will harness Crowdhelix's unique AI-powered recommender engine to establish an online community that will shape the future of our profession. The Helix will also give you access to valuable learning resources and professional development opportunities that can help you advance your career.

How do I join?

Visit the Research Management Helix on the Crowdhelix website www.crowdhelix.com. You can also speak with members of the Crowdhelix team at the EARMA conference.

Scan here to join the Research Management Helix, learn more about the platform and connect with our team

hello@crowdhelix.com
www.crowdhelix.com

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

Annex 2 RM ROADMAP Sessions at EARMA 2023

A summary of the 4 Sessions for RM ROADMAP at the EARMA International Conference in Prague in 2023.

The screenshots show the following content:

- Top Left:** EARMA Conference Prague 2023 banner with dates April 24-26, 2023. Navigation links: Partners, Terms and Conditions, Programme Legend, Conference Prices, Programme.
- Top Right:** Session description for 'RM ROADMAP In Depth'. It is a Wednesday 26 April 2-4:45 p.m. session. Description: 'A description of how the RM ROADMAP project works... Category: Open | Topic: Professional Development and Recognition'. It lists four sessions: 1. Co-Creation Exercises, 2. Research Management Helix, 3. Action 17 and pilot projects, 4. RM Roadmap in Depth.
- Bottom Left:** 'Presenters' list including Nik Claesen, Virág Zsár, Carolina Varela, and Borana Taraj.
- Bottom Right:** Session description for 'The Research Management Helix (RM)'. It is a Wednesday 26 April 2-4:45 p.m. session. Description: 'WPI covers among other things the definition of research management, the skills and competences, what research managers do... WP2 covers the available training, networking, mobility and funding options today and how that can evolve in the future... WP3 covers the role and value of research managers to the R&I system and how we make a plan for the future of research management'.

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

8:32:03, 6:32 PM programme **Roadmap)**
 By CrowdHelix and EARMA
 Category: Presentation | Topic: Professional Development and Recognition
 Tuesday 25 April 2:15 p.m. - 2:45 p.m. (Europe/Prague) (Expired)
 North Hall

In this presentation CrowdHelix will explain and demonstrate their new Research Management Helix. This Helix is being launched during the conference as an integral part of the RM Roadmap project and designed for use by the research management community. It will act as the main dissemination channel for RM Roadmap but also feature other research management posts, opportunities and training possibilities

Presentations and Q&A by:

- David Langley (CrowdHelix, Chief of Strategy)
- Cala Jurgens (CrowdHelix, Network Development Lead,)
- Nikl Claesen (EARMA Managing Director)

The RM Roadmap project is a Horizon Europe funded CSA project. It is a pilot project underpinning ERA Action 17 (Research Management Initiative). The goal of the project and Action 17 are to give direction to research management in Europe. Please find more information here:
<https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>

Please find the 4 sessions related to RM Roadmap at the conference here:

1. Co-Creation Exercise
2. Research Management Helix

8:32:03, 6:32 PM programme **3. Action 17 and pilot projects**
4. RM Roadmap in Depth

Presenters

- David Langley
- Mr Cala Jurgens
- Nikl Claesen

 Contact us Terms & conditions Privacy statement
 83305-2023 EARMA GDPR

8:32:03, 6:32 PM programme **EARMA**
 EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH MANAGERS AND ADMINISTRATORS

 EARMA Conference Prague April 24-26, 2023

EARMA Conference Prague 2023

- Partners
- Terms and Conditions
- Programme Legend
- Conference Prices
- Programme

Conference RM ROADMAP Co-Creation And

8:32:03, 6:32 PM programme **Ambassadors**
 Category: Presentation | Topic: Professional Development and Recognition
 Tuesday 25 April 1:45 p.m. - 2:15 p.m. (Europe/Prague) (Expired)
 North Hall

This session will give an overview of the Co-Creation exercise in the Research Management Roadmap Project (RM Roadmap). This co-creation will be made possible through a network of over 100 ambassadors across over 40 countries in Europe.

The RM Roadmap project is a Horizon Europe funded CSA project. It is a pilot project underpinning ERA Action 17 (Research Management Initiative). The goal of the project and Action 17 are to give direction to research management in Europe. Please find more information here:
<https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>

Please find the 4 sessions related to RM Roadmap at the conference here:

1. Co-Creation Exercise
2. Research Management Helix
3. Action 17 and pilot projects
4. RM Roadmap in Depth

Presenters

- Nikl Claesen
- Olaf Svenningaen

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

Navigation and Contact:

- RM ROADMAP Co-Creation and Ambassadors | online
- Dr Evelina Brännvall
- Borana Tanaj
- Contact us
- Terms & conditions
- Privacy statement
- GDPR

EARMA Conference Prague 2023

April 24-26, 2023

EARMA Conference Prague 2023

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In The ERA

Action 17, RM Roadmap and Cardea
Category: Oral | 60 Mins | Topic: None

Tuesday 25 April 3 p.m. - 4 p.m.
(Europe/Prague) (Expired)

Panorama Hall

Research Management Momentum in the ERA:
Action 17, RM Roadmap and CARDEA

There is a very strong research management momentum in Europe. This session will give an overview of the EU policy developed in action 17 by the EC and the stakeholders of the action. The action will be underpinned by two projects of which one is coordinated by EARMA. These projects are RM ROADMAP (<https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>) and CARDEA (<https://www.ucc.ie/en/ie/research/university-humanresources-research/>).

You will get an insight into the policy and how both projects mean to contribute and create impact on research management.

This session will be moderated by Borana Tanaj.

Speakers:

- Action 17: Stijn Delaure (EC, DG R&I, Unit A3, R&I Actions and Research Careers)
- RM Roadmap: Nik Claesen (EARMA, Managing Director)
- CARDEA: Prof. Eduard Balbuena (Professor Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona and ICERCA)

The RM Roadmap project is a Horizon Europe funded CSA project. It is a pilot project underpinning ERA Action 17 (Research Management initiative). The goal of the project and Action 17 are to give direction to research management in Europe. Please find more information here: <https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>

Please find the 4 sessions related to RM Roadmap at the conference here:

1. Co-Creation Exercise
2. Research Management Helix
3. Action 17 and pilot projects
4. RM Roadmap in Depth

Presenters

- Nik Claesen
- Stijn Delaure
- Prof Dr Eduard Balbuena

Moderators

- Borana Tanaj

Annex 3 RM ROADMAP Sessions at EARMA Conference Odense 2024

Two specific sessions on the RM Roadmap Project at the EARMA Conference in Odense in 2024.

The RM Roadmap Project and the ERA Action 17

📅 Apr 24, 02:30 PM - 03:30 PM
📍 SUITCASE

4. Other Format: Oral 60 Minutes Experience Level: 2 PROFESS

This session will give an overview of the RM Roadmap project and make connections with ERA Action 17 (Research Management Initiative). The session will start with an interview with the RM Roadmap coordinators Borana Taraj and Nik Claesen from EARMA about their experiences running this project, the ambassador network of RM Roadmap and the impact they are expecting the project to make. After the double interview, a panel of project partners will discuss the progress of the project to date and the first outcomes as well as reflect on what is to come.

Speaker
Mr Nik Claesen
EARMA

Speaker
Borana Taraj
Head of EU project, EARMA

Speaker
Mx Virág Zsár
Senior Grant Advisor, Hétfő Research Institute

Speaker
Mx Cristina Oliveira
Executive Research Manager of the Information Management Research Center (MagiC), NOVA Information Management School

Speaker
Michael Browne
CrowdHelix

Chair
Sarah Richardson
Editor-in-Chief and Director, Research Professional News, Clarivate

Speaker
Olaf Svenningsen
EARMA

The future of research management: EARMA, RM Roadmap and ERA Action 17

📅 Apr 25, 04:30 PM - 05:00 PM
📍 SUITCASE

Format: Oral 30 Minutes PROFESSIONAL AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT

Please join Nik Claesen, EARMA Managing Director, for an informal session about his perspectives on the future of research management. The topics discussed will be what is happening in Europe currently, with a focus on EARMA, RM Roadmap and ERA Action 17 (The Research Management Initiative). This session will be a more informal, practical and philosophical behind the scenes look with possibilities for input from the audience.

Speaker
Mr Nik Claesen
EARMA

Annex 4 RM ROADMAP Session at INORMS 2025

RM ROADMAP: A Community-driven Vision for the Future of Research Management

📅 May 8, 11:00 AM - 12:00 PM
📍 Amsterdam

EARMA

Format: Oral 60 Minute

Geography: Europe

Floorplan: L

As RM ROADMAP comes to a close, this session will highlight the project's key achievements and the challenges it has faced along the way. It will show how research managers, institutions, and policymakers worked together to co-create important resources: shared guidelines, recommendations, and an interactive Knowledge and Community Platform.

Join us for a lively discussion with RM ROADMAP Ambassadors as they share their experiences and insights on how these efforts are helping to shape the future of research management in Europe.

Read more info: <https://earma.org/abstracts/submission/1180/view/>

Speaker

Nik Claesen

European Association of Research Managers and Administrators

Speaker

Michael Browne

CEO Crowdhelix, Crowdhelix

Speaker

Janina Bau

EU Projects Officer and Research Analyst, EARMA

Speaker

Virág Zsár

HETFA Research Institute Ltd.

Chair

Teodora Konach

Head of Professional Development, EARMA

Speaker

Cristina Oliveira

Executive Research Manager, NOVA Information Management School (NOVA IMS)

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Annex 5 RM ROADMAP Visuals Created for INORMS 2025

Annex 6 RM ROADMAP Survey Results One-Pagers

Survey Results

1 Who are Research Managers?

This page summarises the basic demographical character of Research Managers responding to our survey.

Main messages:

Three-quarters of Research Managers are women. The majority of them are between 35 and 54 years old and half of them have spent at least 10 years in the profession. Research Managers across Europe primarily speak English as a foreign language, and the majority of them confirmed the importance of English knowledge for their job.

A total of 3,069 responses were received by the closure of the questionnaire. Following the screening process, 2,212 respondents' responses were entered into the database.

The RM ROADMAP survey confirms the results of previous surveys (RAAAP, CARDEA), according to which Research Management across Europe are predominantly carried out by women (74.10% of the respondents are female).

An important achievement of our survey is that the sample presents a representative sample of Research Managers across Europe in terms of geography; half of the respondents are based in Western and Northern Europe, while the other half are in Southern, Central and Eastern Europe, as well as in non-EU countries.

Nevertheless, there are differences among countries' representation: 100 respondents or more were from Spain, the United Kingdom, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Italy, respectively; while Finland, Norway, Belgium, Ireland, Turkey, Denmark and Poland had over 50 respondents.

The majority of Research Managers can be considered middle-aged, as they are between 35 and 54 years old (75%). Respondents have been engaged in the field of Research Management for an average of 9.5 years: more than two-thirds of them are working in the profession for at least 5 years, but generally more.

Research Managers primarily speak English as a foreign language, at least as independent users, but some as proficient users indicating the dominance of the English language in the field of RM. English is also considered by the majority of respondents (63%) as important for their job. Besides English, Spanish, French and German are spoken mainly by Research Managers, but none of these languages are considered important for the job itself.

Survey Results

2 Where do Research Managers Work?

This page summarises the characteristics of organisations employing Research Managers having responded to our survey.

Main messages:

Research Managers across Europe work in a great variety of organisations, primarily in universities and research institutions, but also at other types of organisations, including private companies, private non-profit companies and research funders.

The variety of the employer organisations is also demonstrated by the number of employees of these organisations. We can find Research Managers at a huge diversity of Research Performing Organisations, starting from small companies and NGOs to universities employing several thousands of staff.

Most Research Managers work at the central level of their organisation and tend to cover less specific areas than their colleagues at the decentralised levels. This suggests that Research Managers at the departmental level tend to provide more diverse support, while on the central level rather focused support.

Most of our Research Managers work in public organisations (76%), while 14% work in non-profit private and 6% in private organisations or companies. The fact that the RM Roadmap survey could engage a broader group of Research Managers working beyond the public sphere can be considered a great achievement.

This is also demonstrated by the fact that beyond universities, colleges and research institutions, a certain proportion is employed at other types of organisations, such as private companies and research funders. Approximately one-third of Research Managers were affiliated with a top-tier university, while an additional 22% were employed at a research-active university and a further 7% were engaged at a primarily teaching university.

The diversity of the employer organisations is also demonstrated by the fact that the number of employees shows a huge diversity and the different sizes are represented proportionately. Interestingly no major correlation can be found between the size of the organisation and the areas covered by Research Managers in their everyday work, so the size does not necessarily imply specification.

Most Research Managers work at the central level of their organisation (58.63%), while less than one-quarter of them work at departmental level (22.78%). Research Managers working at the central level tend to cover fewer areas in Research Management than their colleagues at the decentral level. While 30% of Research Managers at the central level cover a maximum of 2 different RM areas, the same proportion at the departmental level can cover 3 different RM areas. This suggests that RMs at the departmental level tend to provide more diverse support, while on the central level rather focused support.

Survey Results

4 Areas of Research Management

This page summarises the areas of Research Management based on the RM ROADMAP survey and the 2nd co-creation exercise under the title "Who are Research Managers? Skill and Competences".

Main messages:

Research Managers work in a huge diversity of fields along the whole stream of research, while most of them cover (at least) proposal development (pre-award) and project support and management (post-award). Research Management covers other fields too, such as Research Strategy and Policy Development, Research Support Delivery, Training and Researcher Development, as well, as International Collaboration and institution branding.

Only a small portion of Research Managers covers only one area in their daily work, while a quarter of them cover 2 or even 3 different RM areas. All these underline the fluid, flexible nature of the profession, the diverse and complex activities, the shifting environments, the blended and constantly emerging roles in Research Management.

Identifying the main areas of Research Management is important for defining the profession. Our survey results show that Research Managers work in a huge diversity of fields along the whole stream of research, while most of them cover (at least) proposal development (pre-award, 70%) and project support and management (post-award, 64%). But Research management is nowadays much more than only pre-award and post-award: several RMs also work in Research Strategy and Policy Development (46%), Research Support Delivery (42%), Training and Researcher Development (38%), as well, as International Collaboration, Institution branding (33%).

Only a small portion (10.3%) covers only one RM area in their daily work, while a quarter of them (24.4%) cover 2 or even 3 different RM areas, while another quarter (25%) cover 4 or even 5 different areas.

The 2nd co-creation exercise of the RM ROADMAP aimed to validate the preliminary results of the survey regarding the areas covered by Research Managers aiming to pave the way for the common definition. While agreeing with the multifaceted and complex job roles of RMs, national and thematic groups mentioned that the following sub-areas could be considered as separate areas of Research Management:

- financial management and advising,
- legal advising, contract management, ensuring compliance;
- management of and advising on open science;
- AI and emerging, technologies;
- collaboration with other stakeholders;
- impact management.

Secondly, the outcomes of the consensus documents suggest that

- management of human resources could be the overarching category including the training, and career development of researchers and RMs as well as taking care of mental health;
- innovation management and business development could be merged and could replace the existing categories of "Translation of Results: Uptake and Utilisation" and "Collaboration with the industry".

Survey Results

5 Seeking for a European term preferred by Research Managers

This page summarises Research Managers' preferences towards a common terminology of the profession based on the RM Roadmap survey and the 2nd co-creation exercise under the title "Who are Research Managers? Skill and Competences".

Main messages:

European Research Managers' most preferred 3 umbrella / collective terms are

- 1) Research Manager and Administrator,
- 2) Research Manager, and
- 3) Research Management and Support Professional.

The co-creation session altered slightly the results, bringing Research Managers to the top and shifting RMA to the second place. Both have their merits and drawbacks, and certain geographical differences can also be observed. These differences shall not be reflected in the consensual European term but rather at national levels.

The professional recognition of Research Management necessitates a common terminology that is used and understood not only by professionals but the relevant stakeholders. According to the RM Roadmap survey, Research Managers' most preferred 3 umbrella / collective terms are 1) Research Manager and Administrator, 2) Research Manager, and 3) Research Management and Support Professional.

Based on the survey, certain regional specificities can be observed regarding the preferred terminology.

Northern Europe (IC, NO, SE, DK, FI)	Western Europe (DE, BE, NL, LU, UK, IE, AT, CH)	Southern Europe (PT, ES, IT, MT, CY, EL, FR)	Central and Eastern Europe (EE, LT, LV, PL, SK, CZ, HU, SI, RO, HR, BG)	Non-EU countries (SRB, BiH, MK, MNE, AL, UA, MD, Kosovo, TR)
Research Advisor	Research Manager	Research Manager	Research Manager and Administrator	Knowledge/Technology Management Professional
Research Support Professional	Research Management and Support Professional	Research Manager and Administrator	Research Management and Support Professional	Research Enabler
Research Administrator	Research Manager and Administrator	Research Management and Support Professional	Research Manager	Research Developer

During the co-creation session, Research Manager was ranked at first place by 14 countries and 3 thematic communities, while at second place by 2 countries.

Research Managers and Administrator was ranked at first place by 10 countries and 1 thematic community, while at second place by 6 countries.

To a certain extent, some geographical patterns can be observed: communities from Southern Europe prioritised almost unanimously the term Research Management and put RMA in second place, which was prioritised by Northern European communities.

The terms Research Management and Support Professional was favoured at first place by the 4 national communities, while Research Support Professional generally appeared in third or fourth place, except for one country putting it in first place.

Survey Results

6 Employment Conditions of Research Managers

This page summarises the main characteristics of employment conditions of Research Managers based on the results of the RM Roadmap survey.

Main messages:

Compared to previous surveys, our results show positive trends in Research Managers' employment conditions and characteristics.

An overwhelming majority of respondents have permanent contracts (74%) meaning that they are not employed anymore on a project basis; only 22% of the respondents have fixed time contracts.

The majority identifies themselves as full-time research managers (63%). 19% are employed full-time but combining research management with other roles, 9% with academic roles and almost 10% with other non-academic roles. It is notable that self-employment and other forms of employment are relatively uncommon.

Compared to previous surveys, our results show positive trends in Research Managers' employment conditions and characteristics. Full-time employment is the most common among the respondents (82%); only about a tenth have a part-time job contract. An overwhelming majority have permanent contracts (74%) meaning that they are not employed anymore on a project basis; only 22% of the respondents have fixed time contracts and 11% have secondment.

Type of job carried out by respondents (n=2212)

Contract type (n=2206)

In terms of employment, the majority of respondents identify themselves as full-time research managers (63%). Another 19% are employed full-time but combined research management with other roles, 9% with academic roles and almost 10% with non-academic roles. A total of 7% of respondents indicated that they are employed on a part-time basis as research managers, while a further 4% are employed on a part-time basis and concurrently assumed a managerial role in addition to other academic or non-academic roles. It is notable that self-employment and other forms of employment are relatively uncommon.

We found minor regional variations in employment patterns. Full-time employment is more prevalent in Northern and Southern Europe (88% and 90% compared to 82% for the total sample). Conversely, in Eastern Europe and outside the EU, self-employment and other forms are slightly more common (3% and 6% respectively compared to 2% of the total sample); while the share of part-time workers is higher in Western Europe.

Type of employment along the country groups (n=1780)

Survey Results

7 Working Conditions of Research Managers

This page summarises certain aspects of Research Managers' working conditions based on the results of the RM Roadmap survey.

Main messages:

Working from home is a common practice among RM professionals, as 86% confirmed that they work in this way. 60% of respondents regularly spend time travelling and attending meetings abroad.

Only one-third of Research Managers (35%) have not experienced significant overtime outside the limits of their formal contract. A notable proportion have not only worked overtime but have not received any form of compensation from their employer for the overtime they have worked (27%). 29% of the respondents are able to convert their overtime to days off while a tiny proportion (3%) receive financial compensation.

We aimed to get an understanding of the average time spent practically by Research Managers on their daily job. The average number of hours worked during a week by respondents is 37, with an average of 24 hours spent in the office or laboratory, 13.5 hours spent working from home, and an average of 3 hours per week spent travelling and attending meetings abroad. Working from home is a common practice among RM professionals, with 86% of them reporting that they also work in this way. Furthermore, 60% of respondents regularly spend time travelling and attending meetings abroad. On average, they spend 1-1.5 days abroad per month.

Research Managers reported a diverse range of weekly time-use patterns, influenced by their employment contracts. By definition, full-time respondents dedicate a greater proportion of their time to RM activities than part-time respondents. Additionally, they spend more time in the office and laboratory. However, the time required for working from home is not significantly different from that of part-time employees. Part-time workers also undertake slightly more travel for meetings held abroad.

Another crucial issue is working overtime. The results indicate that only about one-third of Research Managers (35%) have not experienced significant overtime outside the limits of their formal contract. However, a notable proportion of respondents have not only worked overtime but have not received any form of compensation from their employer for the overtime they have worked (27%). A total of 29% of the respondents are able to convert their overtime to days off. Furthermore, there is only a tiny proportion of Research Managers (3%) who receive financial compensation for the overtime they have worked.

Lastly, the survey data reveals disparities in the prevalence of overtime across regions. A lower incidence of overtime is observed in Central and Eastern Europe and in European countries not belonging to the EU. However, in these regions and in Southern Europe, instances of uncompensated overtime were most prevalent. No significant differences are observed by gender, age or type of employment contract.

Survey Results

8 Routes to Research Management and Reasons to Stay

This page summarises how Research Managers get into the profession, why they prefer to stay there and what are their challenges in the profession. The page is based on the results of the RM Roadmap survey.

Main messages:

It is still true that Research Managers "fall into" the profession, due to their skills match or due to the fact that they are interested in working in academia. This fact confirms the developing nature of the profession and the relative unavailability of graduate programmes in Research Management, as it is uncommon for RM professionals to have consciously prepared for a career in RM.

Almost all Research Managers (90%) agree to have a strong motivation to work in the science/academic sector, with a significant proportion (87%) also expressing a desire to support innovation and create new knowledge.

The most prevalent challenge for Research Managers is the lack of clarity regarding the career framework and job architecture (63%). Additionally, over half of the respondents cite the frequent expectation to perform tasks beyond their job description (59%), and the absence of professional recognition (57%).

Similarly to previous surveys, an outstanding majority of Research Managers (81%) agree that a good match of their skills with what is needed in the profession played a key role in their choice of RM career. Approximately half of Research Managers were previously engaged in academic or research activities and subsequently transitioned into a role in research management (46%). This suggests that becoming a professional in Research Management can be an alternative to an academic career. For some, the availability of the position (45%) was the main decisive element, or the RM job opened the door to working at a particular university/college/etc (41%). A mere 19% of respondents indicated that they had been interested in the field during their university studies. In short, Research Managers still fall into the profession. This fact confirms the developing nature of the profession and the relative unavailability of graduate programmes in Research Management, as it is uncommon for RM professionals to have consciously prepared for a career in RM.

What are the incentives for Research Managers to stay in the profession? The two most commonly cited motivational factors are related to the perceived attractiveness of the academic field. Almost all Research Managers (90%) agree to have a strong motivation to work in the science/academic sector, with a significant proportion (87%) also expressing a desire to support innovation and create new knowledge. This is followed by motivational factors related to teamwork, working with people and networking. Then the diverse challenges of the day-to-day tasks are mentioned that make the RM job varied and not boring.

We also aimed to reveal the most significant challenges and difficulties for RM professionals. The responses indicated that challenges related to professional recognition were perceived as more significant, while those related to career opportunities were perceived as less significant. The most prevalent challenge for Research Managers is the lack of clarity regarding the career framework and job architecture (63%). Additionally, over half of the respondents mentions the frequent expectation to perform tasks beyond their job description (59%), the absence of professional recognition (57%), the high-stress environment (57%), the lack of institutional policies (55%), the lack of professional identity (56%), and the lack of opportunities for professional development (51%) as significant obstacles.

As regards the expectations of Research Managers for career advancement, the aspiration for promotion towards leadership is the most common (46%), but approximately a third of the sample plan to change jobs to another institution (39%), gain experience in mobility (34%), progress through the institutional career ladder (33%) or obtain certification in the profession (31%). 29% of Research Managers need mentoring, while only 10% aim at acquiring a doctorate. As anticipated, a higher proportion of respondents with less experience plan to take steps to develop their careers, with a greater need for a change of job, obtaining a certificate and mentoring. They are also more likely to plan to complete a doctorate.

Survey Results

9 Skills & Competences of Research Managers

This page summarises the most important skills and competencies based on the findings of the RM Roadmap survey and the 2nd co-creation exercise under the title "Who are Research Managers? Skill and Competences"

Main messages:

The most important skills for a career in Research Management

- in the field of transversal skills are problem-solving, written communication, interpersonal skills and multitasking.
- In the field of soft skills are prioritisation, time management, efficiency and effectiveness, reliability and trustworthiness, planning and strategic thinking,
- In the field of hard skills are language proficiency, knowledge of the rules and regulations of funders, and an understanding of research and the research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem.

The importance of specialisation and role-related skills are more dependent on the specific role and area in which Research Managers work.

Research Managers responding to the RM Roadmap survey agree that the skills and competencies in the area of transversal skills are considered to be the most important skills group. Among transversal skills, problem-solving, written communication, interpersonal skills and multitasking were considered to be the most important. The order of the skills required for career progression in RM differs slightly from that typically observed: the three most important transversal skills for advancement are problem-solving, self-motivation and interpersonal skills. These are more closely aligned with the skills typically expected of managers in higher positions.

The most important soft skills required for a career in RM are prioritisation, time management, efficiency and effectiveness, reliability and trustworthiness, as well as planning and strategic thinking. The order of skills required for career advancement showed a significant difference, with the most important being planning, strategic thinking, leadership and decision-making, and diplomatic skills. These skills strongly overlap with the skills required for any managerial position.

In the domain of hard skills, language proficiency is of paramount importance, particularly in the case of English. In addition, knowledge of the rules and regulations of funders, an understanding of research and the research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem, and an appreciation of institutional governance are also essential skills. Among the skills deemed essential for promotion, an understanding of research and the R&I ecosystem, an understanding of institutional governance, and management skills were identified as the most crucial.

The importance of specialisation and role-related skills are more dependent on the specific role or area in which Research Managers work. In general, the most importance skills are administrative skills, the ability to build and maintain networks, stakeholder engagement and management, and the capacity to appreciate values and understand interests.

Outcomes of the 2nd co-creation exercise:

There are several 'horizontal' skills and competencies that are needed by most RMs. These skills and competencies are related to their core role, namely supporting – and not conducting – research. These skills are the following:

- Among transversal skills: critical thinking, communication, interpersonal thinking, proactivity, cultural and diversity skills, problem-solving,
- Among soft skills: leadership skills, creative thinking, analytical thinking, facilitation, curiosity, resilience, conflict management and resolution, strategic thinking,
- Among hard skills: IT skills, digital literacy, AI skills.

Once these denominators are defined, it is important to identify the specific skills and competencies for the specialised fields and job roles in RM.

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Annex 7 RM ROADMAP Website Analytics

RM Roadmap Website Analytics

<u>Period</u> M1-M32	<u>Website Visits</u> 90,960
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Traffic (Second Reporting Period)

VISITS 68K -8% yr/yr	BOUNCE RATE 93.38% +0% yr/yr	UNIQUE VISITORS 65K -9% yr/yr	PAGEVIEWS 57K +9% yr/yr
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Visits

Sep 1, 2023–Jun 18, 2025 • 67,701 Total -8% yr/yr

Monthly ▼

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

Geography

Visits by Country

Sep 1, 2023–Jun 18, 2025 • 67,997 Total

Location	Visits
▶ Belgium	8,203 (12.1%)
▶ Spain	6,118 (9.00%)
▶ France	4,237 (6.23%)
▶ Portugal	4,093 (6.02%)
▶ Italy	3,531 (5.19%)
▶ Netherlands	3,240 (4.76%)
▶ Germany	3,235 (4.76%)
▶ United Kingdom	3,205 (4.71%)
▶ Turkey	3,166 (4.66%)
▶ Ireland	2,904 (4.27%)

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▶ United States	2,640 (3.88%)
▶ Croatia	1,817 (2.67%)
▶ Czechia	1,731 (2.55%)
▶ Hungary	1,718 (2.53%)
▶ Poland	1,641 (2.41%)
▶ Austria	1,368 (2.01%)
▶ Norway	1,267 (1.86%)
▶ Denmark	1,214 (1.79%)
▶ Greece	1,174 (1.73%)
▶ Cyprus	1,172 (1.72%)

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Traffic Sources

VISITS 68K	REVENUE €0	CHECKOUTS 0	CONV. RATE 0%	AOV €0	RPV €0
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Visits

Sep 1, 2023–Jun 18, 2025 • 67,701 Total

Monthly ▼

Top Sources by Visits [VIEW SOURCES](#)

TOP SOURCES

Source	Visits	Revenue	Checkouts	Conv. Rate	AOV	RPV
Direct	56,091 (82.9%)	€0.00	0	0.0%	€0.00	€0.00
▶ Search	7,334 (10.8%)	€0.00	0	0.0%	€0.00	€0.00
▶ Referral	2,332 (3.44%)	€0.00	0	0.0%	€0.00	€0.00
▶ Social	1,695 (2.50%)	€0.00	0	0.0%	€0.00	€0.00
▶ Email	249 (0.37%)	€0.00	0	0.0%	€0.00	€0.00

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

Site Content

Top Pageviews

Sep 1, 2023–Jun 18, 2025 • 90% of 57,184 Pageviews +0% yr/yr

All Pages with Views

Sep 1, 2023–Jun 18, 2025 • 57,184 Total +0% yr/yr

Page	Views	Time on Page	Bounce Rate	Exit Rate
Home	26,273	00:02:03	93.42%	88.9%
Ambassador Programme /faq	6,430	00:02:53	93.69%	84.31%
Co-Creation Results /co-creation-results	4,553	00:02:46	95.6%	84.1%
Community Connect /community-connect	4,254	00:02:02	93.02%	73.93%
Project Workflow /project-workflow	3,655	00:01:31	90.23%	72.75%
Deliverables /deliverables	2,601	00:02:20	94.62%	78.93%
News & Events /news-events	1,943	00:01:00	89.5%	66.8%
RM Professional Development Opportunities /rm-professional-development-opportunities	1,559	00:02:32	95.61%	85.38%
Ambassador Programme /ambassadors	1,525	00:02:20	89.94%	77.51%
RM Roadmap Knowledge and Community Platform - How to Engage on the New EARMA Online /news-events/d4kjt2c0rpos38s9jz3s07l3axvul	796	00:03:47	95.25%	84.55%

Annex 8 RM ROADMAP Social Media Analytics

RM ROADMAP Social Media Analytics

LinkedIn

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
Reporting Period 2 (19 June 2024-now)	62,354	8.6%

Followers of the LinkedIn Page

Follower metrics

Figure 26- Total follower growth from May 2024- May 2025

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

Visitors to the LinkedIn Page

Visitor highlights ?

1,917
Page views

1,031
Unique visitors

2
Custom button clicks

Visitor metrics ?

Page views ▼ | All pages ▼ | All filters

Desktop 1,243

Mobile 674

Figure 27-Visitors to the LinkedIn Page from May 2024-May 2025

X/Twitter

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
Reporting Period 2 (1 September 2023-now)	27,177	N/A

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.6_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

Annex 9 Research Management Helix Statistics (March 2023- May 2025)

Posts Created in Helix

Users Subscribed to Helix

Private messages by Users subscribed to Helix

RM ROADMAP

 rmroadmap.eu

 [@rmroadmap](https://twitter.com/rmroadmap)

 linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap

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